

Comparative Analysis of Social Media and Peer influence on Risky Behaviours among Colleges of Education Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined social media and peer influence as predictors of risky behaviours among the colleges of education students in Osun State, Nigeria. The population consisted of all colleges of education students in Osun state, Nigeria with the sample of 510 including Part I and II students who were purposively selected from three colleges of education in Osun State, Nigeria. Multistage Sampling Procedure was used which consisted of stratified, purposive and simple random sampling techniques. A validated adapted instruments titled Risky Behaviour Scale (RBS) and Peer and Social Media Influence Scale (PSIS) were used to elicit information from the students. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. The results revealed that there is moderate effect of social media and peer influence on students' involvement in risky behaviour. Also, the level at which the Colleges of Education students engage in risky behaviour is very high. It is recommended that awareness should be created on risky behaviour to mitigate the involvement of students in such act.

Keyword: Risky behaviour, social media, peer influence, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Colleges of Education have a rich history rooted in the evolution of educational system globally which can be traced back to the early 20th century and Nigeria government played significant role in the establishment and development of colleges of education with the aim of enhancing the quality of teacher and education. Therefore, being admitted into the college of education is not the only criterion of becoming a teacher but the required coping skill the students develop to resist distractions which comes with lots of challenges which can adversely affect their studies and career. Many students come to the college of education unaware of the challenges awaiting them which include meeting different people from different background, changing of environment, associating with the staff and buildings of the college that requires coping strategies. However, these circumstances are new to many of them, they cannot be avoided; they are still apparently academic realities that each student must contend with in order to succeed academically in the ivory tower of intellectualism; as a result, they have an impact on how they carry out their responsibilities as students and their overall performance. Therefore many of them ended up in participating in risky behaviour such as smoking, truancy, consumption of alcohol, sexual activities, self-harm, use of weapons and cybercrimes as coping strategies which consequently affects how they discharge their duties as students.

In recent years, students particularly College of Education students (COEs) partake in **risky behaviours** which form attitudes that culminate into career jeopardy. They are behaviours that blind students from seeing the reality and beauty of academic environment and achievement. Also, risky behaviours are defined by researchers as behaviours that can cause harm or pose a substantial risk of danger, hinder individuals from achieving their full potential, or markedly diminish their independence or longevity. This explains how students risk their lives participating in harmful activities which consequently has adverse effect on their studies and lives. The inclination to engage in risky behaviour is especially high during adolescence, where identity exploration and cognitive immaturity may lead to poor decision-making. It had also been researched that these behaviours are the ones distracting the students from their primary assignment in the college which invariably affect their studies and degrading the potentials of becoming great teachers. This also consequently depreciates the value of prospective teachers who are to tutor the future and glory of the country.

In addition, it was researched that risky behaviours are voluntary actions with a high probability of negative consequences, such as injury, legal trouble, or social disapproval. These behaviors, such as drug abuse and unprotected sex, are typically influenced by developmental factors like peer pressure and emotional instability. Steinberg (2017) emphasizes the role of adolescent brain development, particularly the underdeveloped prefrontal cortex, which results in impulsive and risky decision-making. Arnett (2015) in his own view explains that risky behaviors are common during the period of "emerging adulthood" and are a result of the psychological and social pressures of forming an independent identity. Therefore, risky behaviors are actions undertaken by individuals, particularly adolescents, as part of social interactions and identity exploration. Behaviors like drug use, skipping school, and early sexual activity are often driven by peer influence and the desire to fit in

with certain social groups, as well as the natural inclination of adolescents to test boundaries and establish autonomy. This is prevalent because some students are not aware of the consequences while some are aware of the consequences but want to satisfy their curiosity which is drastically affecting their academic well-being.

According to Amita and Apter (2012), risky behaviours are behavioural activities that threaten social order. They opined that despite the actions taken in the past three decades, these behaviours have grown exponentially worldwide. This explains how these behaviours are spreading like wildfire in the dry forest during dry season. The experiences and exposure gained by an individual before entering the college of education will not completely help them function efficiently in the new environment; some of these experiences have to be reinforced, some have to be unlearned while others to be blended with the new experiences garnered in the college of education environment. This is because the college of education is a dynamic environment that requires a dynamic approach to live in it. However, risky behaviours like betting, use of alcohol and sexual activities are very common among the COE students and it is of course worthy of researching. It had also been researched that the influential of risky behaviours are enormous but for the purpose of this study, peer influence and social media were chosen as predictors of risky behaviours.

Therefore, social media is a virtual community that brings together individuals with similar interest, beliefs and values. It is a platform where people can acquire new knowledge, challenge existing beliefs, or undergo relearning experiences, both in positive and negative aspects. It is a space where risky behaviours can be transmitted from one person to another. It is also an avenue or space where individual can learn, unlearn and relearn. In another view, social media is a digital tool that promotes interactive communication and networking through user-generated content, changing social and educational interactions. This implies that through social media, students form lots of interactive activities which can either make or mar their academic well-being. It is still the sole platform where many individuals can interact continuously. Through virtual communities and networks, social media, as described by researchers is a computer-mediated technology that makes it easier to create and share ideas, information, career interests, and other forms of expression. This clarifies how information is sent when the sender and the recipient are not in immediate physical proximity.

Furthermore, the pervasive influence of social media on adolescents and young adults has raised questions about how it promotes risky behaviours including gambling, sexual activities and use of alcohol. However, recent studies have looked at how social media use can contribute to these behaviours as well as the psychological and social elements that raise their prevalence. Exposure to social media is also directly linked to dangerous conduct, according to research. A systematic review by Susi et al. (2023) found that susceptible users' self-harm tendencies can be both worsened and reinforced when they watch images of self-harm on social media. According to the study, social media encourages identity building and social comparisons around self-harming activities, frequently reinforcing bad behaviours through interactions with other members of the community. Nevertheless, risky conduct has changed as a result of social media and gambling coming together. In their examination of the digital convergence of gambling, gaming, and cryptocurrencies, Delfabbro and King (2023) showed how gambling-like elements in video games, including loot boxes, might expose young people to gambling at an early age and even normalize it.

In contrast, peer influence which is believed to be one of the components influencing dangerous behaviour is referred to as an individual's behaviour being altered, either positively or negatively, in order to be accepted and respected by colleagues, peers, or acquaintances. Peer influence involves the alteration of one's beliefs, thoughts, values and ideas by individual at a similar level or status. This behaviour can be explained using normative social influence, where individuals conform to be accepted or liked by the group. Asch's conformity studies also demonstrate how people often agree with the majority, even if they believe they are wrong in order to avoid been rejected. However, peer influence is believed to be one of the agents of socialization that plays a crucial role in shaping behaviours during adolescence and young adulthood. According to Okafor and Alabi (2020), peer pressure is especially strong in social and academic contexts, where students are frequently motivated by a desire to blend in or win their peers' approval, which pushes them to engage in risky behaviors like unprotected intimate relationships in an effort to conform to group norms.

In addition, students who have drinking friends around them are much more likely to start drinking and keep drinking. Even after taking personality and family factors into consideration. A longitudinal study by Schulenberg et al. (2020) discovered that peer alcohol consumption predicts the frequency and amount of drinking among college students. This argument can be buttressed with the social learning theory which reveals that people imitate the behaviours of their peer groups, particularly when those behaviours are rewarded by the group. Also, peers can influence sexual decision-making by establishing behavioural norms and influencing attitudes about sexual engagement. However, psychologists revealed that early sexual initiation is more likely when friends talk about their sexual experiences since it is perceived as normal behaviour.

In Nigeria, risky behaviours such as drinking alcohol, gambling, and engaging in dangerous sexual behaviour among the COE students represent a developing public health issue. These actions have far-reaching effects, such as addiction, poor academic performance, health issues, and societal breakdown. Peer pressure and social media are two important factors influencing these habits. Both have a huge and unique impact on young people's views and behaviours. Due to the widespread use of social media, students are exposed to unfiltered content that glorifies risky behaviours including binge drinking, gambling, and casual sexual encounters. Content that supports these behaviors is frequently amplified by social media algorithms, normalizing them and encouraging involvement from impressionable students. Similarly, peer influence plays a critical role in shaping behavioral norms among students. Peers often serve as immediate role models, exerting pressure on others to conform to group behaviours. In the context of risky behaviours, peer pressure can encourage alcohol use, gambling, and unsafe sexual activities, especially when these behaviours perceived as avenues for social acceptance or bonding. Although, there are numerous researches on risky behaviours but much has not been done on both the influence of social media and peer influence as predictors of risky behaviours among the COE students in Osun State, Nigeria, hence this study tend to fill the gap in order to develop effective interventions aimed at promoting healthier choices and resilience against peer and social media pressures.

Objectives of the study

The Objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the level of risky behaviours among the COE students
2. Explore how social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students
3. Access how peer influence contribute to the prevalence of risky behaviours among the COE students

Research Questions

1. What is the level of risky behaviours among the OE students in Nigeria?
2. Does social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students?
3. What is the extent to which peer influence contributes to the development of risky behaviours among the COE students?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant joint relationship between peer influence and social interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive design. The population of the study consisted of all Part I and II COE students in Osun State, Nigeria. Three COE were selected in the state for the study. A federal and a state colleges of education were purposively selected because they were the only federal and state colleges of education as of the time of the study while a private college of education was randomly selected from the private colleges of education in the state using balloting system. The sample size comprised 600 students who were selected randomly using simple random sampling technique while 510 copies of questionnaire were analyzed because some respondent didn't complete theirs. A validated adapted instruments titled Risky Behaviour Scale (RBS) and Peer and Social Media Influence Scale (PSIS) were used to elicit information from the students. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data collected. The reliability test reveals that social media, peer influence and risky behaviours have 0.65, 0.65 and 0.60 respectively.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level risky behaviour among the colleges of Education Students in Osun State?

Table 1: Level of risky behaviour among the colleges of education students

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	I gamble when I am stressed	3.43	1.61	Prevalent
2	I engage in sexual activities without protection with new partners.	3.15	1.61	Prevalent

3	I engage in alcohol consumption despite knowing its risk	3.39	1.61	Prevalent
4	I drink more than I planned during parties.	3.63	1.28	Prevalent
5	I feel anxious if I have not gambled.	3.55	1.34	Prevalent
6	I gamble for money when hanging out.	3.58	1.47	Prevalent
7	I often have multiple sexual partners at once.	2.68	1.58	Not Prevalent
8	I am addicted to sex.	2.12	1.29	Not Prevalent
9	I borrow money to gamble.	2.37	1.45	Not Prevalent
10	I have casual sex without knowing my partner well.	2.37	1.45	Not Prevalent

The data analysis shows that majority of the respondents gamble when they are stressed, hence translating to prevalence of stress-gambling among COE students. Also, a good number of the respondents alluded to the fact that they have unprotected sex with new partners, thus translating to the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour. Similarly, despite knowing the consequences, there is widespread of reckless alcohol consumption among the respondents; this is akin to heavy alcohol consumption during parties. In the same vein, majority of the respondents feel anxious if they have not gambled- this is a pointer to the fact that they have become addicted to the act. Also, the proliferation of gambling among the respondents can be adduced to the desire to have more money. However, sex with multiple partners at once is not prevalent among the respondents, this is the same with addiction to sex, borrowing money to gamble and having unplanned sex with partners they do not know too well. In conclusion, many students resort to gambling as a coping mechanism for stress.

Research Question 2

What is the extent to which social media contribute to the development of risky behaviour?

Table 2: Responses on extent to which social media contributes to the development of risky behaviours

Table 2.1

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S. EE	Change Statistics				Sig.F Change
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	
1	.412 ^a	.170	.168	.61248	.170	103.716	1	508	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), SM_new

Table 2.2

Coefficients^a

Model		Standardized Coefficients			VIF
		Beta	T	Sig.	
1	(Constant)		15.056	.000	
	SM_new	.412	10.184	.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(1, 508)=103.72, P<.001, Adj R^2=0.17$ and $R^2=0.17, (\beta=0.412, t=10.18, P<.001)$, it also shows that the regression model is statistically significant. The analysis shows a moderate effect of social media on students' involvement in risky behaviour- which means that approximately 17% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to social media. In addition to that, for every increase in the usage of social media, risky behaviour will increase by 0.412 units. Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Research Question 2

What is the extent to which peer influence contribute to the development of risky behaviour?

Table 3: The extent to which peer influence contributes to the development of risky behaviours.

Table 3.1

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S. E. E	Change Statistics			Sig.F Change	
					R ² Change	F Change	df1		
1	.426 ^a	.181	.180	.60811	.181	112.541	1	508	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), PI_new

Table 3.2

Coefficients^a

Model		Standardized Coefficients			VIF
		Beta	T	Sig.	
1	(Constant)		11.443	.000	
	PI_new	.426	10.609	.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(1, 508) = 112.54, P < .001$, $Adj R^2 = 0.18$ and $R^2 = 0.18$, ($\beta = 0.426, t = 10.61, P < .001$). The analysis shows a moderate effect of peer influence on students' involvement in risky behaviour- which means that approximately 18% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to peer influence. In addition to that, for every 1-unit increase in peer influence, risky behaviour increases by 0.426 units. Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour.

Table 4: Joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	S. E. E	Change Statistics			Sig.F Change	
					R ² Change	F Change	df1		
1	.513 ^a	.263	.260	.57756	.263	90.460	2	507	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), PI_new, SM_new
b. Dependent Variable: RB_new

Table 5: Coefficients^a

Model		Standardized Coefficients			VIF
		Beta	T	Sig.	
1	(Constant)		11.443	.000	
	SM_new	.303	7.494	.000	1.126
	PI_new	.324	8.018	.000	1.126

Multiple linear regression at 95% confidence interval revealed a good model fit: $F(2, 507) = 90.46, P < .001$, $Adj R^2 = 0.26$ and $R^2 = 0.26$, social media ($\beta = 0.303, t = 7.494, P < .001$) while peer influence ($\beta = 0.324, t = 8.018, P < .001$). The model is statistically significant, indicating a reliable joint influence of social media and peer influence on risky behaviour. Approximately 26% of the variance in risky behaviour is linked to social media and peer influence. In addition to that, for every 1-unit increase in social media usage, risky behaviour increases by 0.303 units, hence increased social media usage culminates into increased risky behaviour. In the same vein, for every 1-unit increase in peer influence, risky behaviour increases by 0.324 units, which shows a positive relationship between peer influence and risky behaviour. Furthermore, both social media and peer influence are significant predictors of risky behaviour, however, peer influence has a stronger relationship with risky behaviour ($\beta = 0.303$ and $\beta = 0.324$ for social media and peer influence respectively) Also, the value of the value inflation factors (VIF) shows no evidence of multi-collinearity in the dataset.

Discussion of Findings

Level of risky behaviour among tertiary institution students in Osun State

The descriptive study, which was carried out to evaluate the prevalence of risky behaviour among the COE s in Osun State, Nigeria indicates alarming tendencies, especially with regard to stress-induced gambling, risky sexual behaviour, and careless alcohol use. These results suggest that there are serious public health issues that need more research and quick action plans. The research shows that many students use gambling as a coping method for stress; in fact, a large percentage of respondents said they gamble when they are under stress. The results of this study are consistent with previous research highlighting the ways in which gambling may be utilized as an unhealthy stress-reduction tactic, ultimately resulting in the emergence of gambling addiction in youth. According to a recent study, internet gambling is frequently linked to finance and mental health issues, especially during difficult times like the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, there is an established relationship between stress, anxiety and gambling since long-term stress can make addictive behaviours worse, including gambling. Similarly, series of improper sexual behaviours among the tertiary institution students had been researched to be associated with a number of factors, including peer pressure, dearth of thorough sexual education, and impulsive decision-making frequently made when intoxicated. This can be linked to bio psychologists who discovered that people with impulsive decision making are tagged to have frontal lobe issues.

It is noteworthy in this study that multiple sex partner and sex addiction are less prevalent. In the same vein, respondents also admitted to drinking alcohol carelessly, especially at gatherings. These findings align with research on alcohol use among students, which emphasizes the prevalence of heavy drinking and excessive alcohol intake at social events, frequently intensifying other dangerous behaviours like careless driving and illicit sexual activity (Elgán et al., 2019). To buttress this, it was posited by a researcher that many students continue to excessively engage in alcohol use despite the negative effects; this behaviour is frequently linked to a need for social approval or as a way to deal with stress from both their academic and private lives. In conclusion, the findings highlight the need to promote safer sexual practices among tertiary institution students in Osun State. It equally addresses stress-related behaviours, especially alcohol and gambling. In order to reduce these harmful behaviours and promote a healthy academic environment, specific interventions like as stress management courses, alcohol moderation campaigns, and comprehensive sexual education should be put instituted.

In other way, it was revealed in the study that social media moderately contribute to the perpetuation of risky behaviours among tertiary institution students in Osun State. This aligns with some previous research works which explains how increased social media use is associated with a higher chance of engaging in risky behaviours, especially for adolescents and young adults. Also, the kinds of content students are exposed to on social media platforms can expose them to activities that encourage risky behaviour. This exposure may cause youth to engage in risky activities because of peer pressure or because such behaviour has become normalized online. In conclusion, results show that social media has a moderate effect size but a considerable impact on students' risky behaviour. Policymakers, teachers, and parents should be aware of possible risks associated with social media use and urge students to use it responsibly as it continues to develop and become more and more integrated into everyday life, particularly for young people.

Extent to which peer influence contributes to risky behaviours

It can be extrapolated from the findings of this study that peer influence contributes notably to risky behaviour among tertiary institution students. These findings align with the social learning theory of Albert Bandura, which posits that individuals learn behaviour through observation, modelling and imitation. Students are therefore more inclined to emulate their peers or directly support peers who engage in dangerous behaviour through association. Hence, these findings have significant effects, especially for interventions and policies meant to discourage students from engaging in risky behaviours. Interventions such as peer-education, mentorship programs and sensitization programs would be successful as peer influence is a major factor in determining students' decisions. Valente (2010) explains the effectiveness of peer-mentoring programmes in influencing changes in behaviour. Peer influence also strongly correlates with the rise of gambling among the COE students in Nigeria. Researchers are of the opinion that students in Nigerian colleges of education who are introduced to gambling by their peers are more likely to adopt the behaviour. This is particularly evident in social gatherings where gambling is viewed as a recreational activity, normalizing what would otherwise be considered deviant behaviour. It had also been researched that factors such as locus of control, low self-esteem, lack of confidence, need for approval, and personality such as agreeableness and openness constitute peer influence.

Significant joint relationship between social media and peer interaction and the perpetuation of risky behaviour

Findings revealed a significant insight into the joint influence of social media and peer influence on the perpetuation of risky behaviour- this is in tandem with existing literatures which establish similar connections. Social media exposure and peer dynamics shape the behaviour of youths; young adults who see their peers participating in risky behaviours on social

media may feel under pressure to follow suit in order to fit in or prevent being excluded from their social group. Social media not only provides a platform for the display and normalization of risky behaviours, it also fosters peer interactions that help reinforce these behaviours. According to Anderson and Jiang (2018), young adults and adolescents commonly discuss experiences linked to drug use, partying, or other types of deviance online, which makes it possible for dangerous behaviours to spread swiftly within peer groups.

Conclusion

It was concluded in this study that risky behaviour of COE students is greatly influenced by the combined effects of peer pressure and social media. Although each of these elements alone increases the likelihood of engaging in risky behaviour, their combined impact is far more significant. Peer pressure pushes people to indulge in harmful behaviours, and social media provide a platform where these behaviours are accepted and lauded, amplifying the power of peers. Also, the findings highlight the need to promote safer sexual practices among the Colleges of Education students in Osun State. It equally addresses stress-related behaviours, especially alcohol and gambling.

Recommendations

1. In order to reduce these harmful behaviours and promote a healthy academic environment, specific interventions like stress management courses, alcohol moderation campaigns, and comprehensive sexual education should be instituted.
2. Policymakers, teachers, and parents should be aware of possible risks associated with social media use and urge students to use it responsibly as it continues to develop and become more and more integrated into everyday life, particularly for young people.
3. Campaigns should be raised on awareness of the dangers of gambling including comprehensive sexual education which are essential for equipping young people to make wise decisions.
4. For students not to be influenced by their peers negatively, counselling unit should be well equipped with professional counsellors and other resources

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